

Beyond Participation: Shaping Meaningful Outcomes in Active Ageing Programs

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Introduction

In Singapore's rapidly ageing society, Active Ageing Centres (AACs) play a key role in supporting seniors' well-being. Most AACs run Active Ageing Programs (AAPs) to promote good health and the fundamental principles of active ageing. However, the evaluation for AAPs is largely output-based, focusing on KPIs like attendance, which do not reflect real improvements in health and may not bring about meaningful outcomes.

Aim: Solve the issue by developing an evaluation framework that could be used to evaluate existing AAC programs to ensure continuous improvement and positive impact over time. We partnered with Tzu Chi@Bukit Batok for this project. Our framework is the Adapted Comprehensive Healthy Ageing Evaluation Framework (ACHAEF).

Strengths	Opportunity	Weakness	Threat
Wide Variety of programs, appealing to many seniors	Ongoing national push for healthy ageing	Held to the standards of larger organisations (AIC)	Some seniors may be hard to reach (unwilling/unable)
Good partnerships with external vendors	AIC supports with funding and resources	KPIs are output-based (attendance)	Resource intensive areas may not be sustainable

Methods

Literature Review

Needs Assessment

Framework Comparison + Selection

Tool Selection and Prototyping

Feedback and Refinement

Results

Fig 1

Motivating factors to come to Tzu Chi

Note: 5 out of 7 seniors mentioned "Programs" as one of their reasons

Table 1

Feedback on completed framework

Areas done well	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Framework is easy to use Covers multiple domains Suitable for mass delivery
Areas for Improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More in-depth comparison needed Accuracy and suitability need to be tested Need to be adapted to fit local contexts

Discussion

- From Fig. 1, most seniors enjoy coming to Tzu Chi for the programs offered, making it important for us to focus our framework on the efficacy of AAPs
- From Table 1, our final framework satisfied the needs of our stakeholders, and serves as a tool for multi-domained evaluation of programs in the AAC, both long- and short-term.
- ACHAEF has the potential to shift AAC evaluation standards and focus if properly developed

Conclusion

In conclusion, our current ACHAEF framework represents a crucial first step towards meaningful evaluation in AACs. By shifting the focus away from solely outcome-based measurements like attendance rates, AACs can focus more on ensuring that they are cultivating real positive change in seniors.

We believe that ACHAEF can be used in Tzu Chi for now, but has the potential to be expanded locally with proper piloting and refinement.

ACHAEF

Short term

- Impact survey (knowledge, attitudes, behaviours)

Long term

- HAQ Questionnaire
- Grip Strength Test
- Blood Pressure measurement
- Wearable Technology

To Supplement the components of the HAQ

BPS

• Physical →

Grip strength
Blood pressure measurement
activPAL wearable (optional)

• Mental →

SAGE test for cognitive(optional)
GDS test for psychological (optional)

• Social →

Track their participation across programs run by Tzu Chi (optional)

References

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